

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FAMILY UPBRINGING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CHILD'S EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. *This article examines the psychological and pedagogical foundations of the development of a child's emotional intelligence within the context of family upbringing. The structure of emotional intelligence is analyzed through the lens of both Russian and international research traditions. The study emphasizes the role of family emotional climate and parent-child interaction as key factors in a child's personal development. Particular attention is paid to father's involvement as a determinant of empathy, emotional responsiveness, and self-regulation in early childhood. Based on a review of current studies, the article substantiates the importance of educational and parenting initiatives that enhance father engagement as a resource for the child's emotional and social well-being.*

Keywords: *emotional intelligence; family upbringing; parental interaction; child's emotional development; fatherhood; empathy; educational practice; psychological and pedagogical conditions.*

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that modern changes in society and education challenge pedagogy and psychology to rethink the role of the family in shaping a child's emotional development. In the context of digitalization, an accelerated pace of life, and increasing information overload, the need for emotional resilience and empathy as components of emotional intelligence is increasing. In this context, family education serves not only as a means of transmitting norms and values but also as a space for shaping the individual's emotional culture. The development of a child's emotional intelligence through family education is a complex and multifaceted psychological and pedagogical phenomenon that requires interdisciplinary analysis. The problem of emotional intelligence lies at the intersection of psychological and pedagogical research and is viewed as a complex personal development that integrates cognitive, motivational, and affective processes.

It is important to note that within the humanistic approach (K. Rogers, A. Maslow, V. Frankl), emotional intelligence is viewed as a central component of personal growth, ensuring inner harmony and the ability to empathically interact. Within the context of the activity-based approach (A. N. Leontiev), the development of a child's emotional competencies occurs through joint activities with adults, which determines the key role of parents in the development of emotional-value relationships [6].

Contemporary researchers emphasize that emotional intelligence is a critical indicator of personal maturity and the success of a person's interactions with the environment. As M. G. Yudina notes, emotional intelligence is "a complex of mental abilities that enable the conscious perception and expression of one's own feelings, understanding and managing the emotional states of others" [10, p. 2]. The author points out that the development of emotional intelligence contributes to the development of such qualities as empathy, tolerance, and communicative flexibility, making it an integral part of harmonious personal development. The definition of "emotional intelligence" is explored in publications by scholars such as D. Goleman, P. Salovey, J. Mayer, D. V. Lyusin, D. V. Ushakov, and others [3; 7; 11].

It is essential to recognize that renowned researcher in the field of emotional intelligence, D. Goleman, points out that the emotional sphere of a person is the most important determinant of the success of human interactions and self-actualization. His concept emphasizes that an individual's ability to recognize, interpret, and regulate their own emotional states, as well as to understand the emotions of others, largely determines the effectiveness of interpersonal communication and the level of adaptation in society. According to the scientist, the development of emotional intelligence is a significant factor in achieving professional and personal success, often surpassing in importance traditional cognitive abilities and IQ [3, p. 58].

Yudina M.G. pays special attention to the fact that emotional intelligence is not only cognitive, but also personal and social in nature: it is formed through the individual's attitude to the surrounding world, as the author notes: "the foundations of this phenomenon are associated with the individual's attitude in society" [10, p. 2]. In her work, N. Yu. Verkhoturova emphasizes that emotional intelligence in a psychological and pedagogical context is interpreted as an integrative system of cognitive and affective abilities that enable the perception, recognition, awareness, and regulation of emotions in oneself and others, as well as their use for constructive interaction and social adaptation [2, p. 114].

The question of the structural organization of emotional intelligence occupies a central place in modern psychological and pedagogical research. Foreign and domestic authors emphasize its multicomponent nature, uniting cognitive, affective, and regulatory aspects of the psyche. Thus, in D. Goleman's model, emotional intelligence is presented as a system of interconnected components—self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills—that ensure adaptive and effective interaction between the individual and the environment [3]. Domestic researchers are clarifying the structure of emotional intelligence in relation to the educational and family environment. N. Yu. Verkhoturova identifies cognitive, emotional-evaluative and regulatory levels, combined into a dynamic system that ensures emotional stability and social adaptation of the individual [2].

It should be highlighted that logical continuation of this theoretical analysis is an appeal to the specifics of the formation of emotional intelligence in the microsocial environment, primarily in the family, which serves as the primary and most significant platform for the emotional and personal development of the child. The family, as the primary social and educational environment, is a natural laboratory for the formation of emotional responsiveness, empathy and the ability to self-regulate. In the domestic psychological and pedagogical literature (A. Ya. Varga, E. O. Smirnova, A. S. Spivakovskaya) it is emphasized that the nature of the emotional relationship between parents and the child determines the stability of emotional reactions, the level of anxiety and the characteristics of the child's communication with peers [1; 8; 9].

Particular attention should be paid to the fact that recent study by Egorova A. I. and Egorov I. V. devoted to the study of the factors of infantilism in youth showed that "i.e., excessive care and guardianship of parents are associated with a high level of sensitivity, susceptibility, dependence of the child and a low level of his independence" [4; [p. 137]. The study conducted during the COVID-2019 pandemic showed that "in families coping stably with the pandemic, adolescents are distinguished by emotional well-being, social activity, and psychologically adaptive behavior" [5; p. 21].

From particular importance is the study of the father's role in the development of a child's emotional intelligence. A number of studies (A. Ya. Varga, A. S. Spivakovskaya, E. O. Smirnova) show that paternal involvement and emotional responsiveness contribute to the development of a child's confidence, emotional stability, and ability to reflect [1; 8; 9]. It is the father who often serves as a model for self-regulation and constructive behavior in emotionally charged situations. For example, E. O. Smirnova notes that a father's active participation in raising a child increases the level of emotional responsiveness, promotes the development of the ability to understand and adequately express emotions, and also develops a readiness for constructive interaction with peers and adults [8].

Conclusion

The conducted analysis allows us to conclude that a child's emotional intelligence is formed in the context of family interaction, where the emotional climate, communication style, and the degree of involvement of parents, especially the father, are of key importance. A harmonious emotional environment promotes the development of empathy, self-regulation, and emotional stability, which ensures successful socialization and personal well-being of the child.

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